

Kinetics and mechanism of silver(I) catalyzed oxidation of alanine by cerium(IV) in perchloric acid medium

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The kinetics of the silver(I) catalyzed oxidation of alanine with cerium(IV) has been studied in perchloric acid medium. An usual decrease in rate with increasing concentration of cerium(IV) is observed and the detailed quantitative analysis of this behaviour is presented on the basis of dimerization of cerium(IV). The reaction exhibits fractional dependence on alanine and that has been accounted for the formation of an adduct with silver(I). A plausible reaction mechanism is given and the rate law is derived

$$k = \frac{k_1 K_1 [LH^+] [H^+]}{[H^+] + [K_1] [1 + K_1 [LH^+]]}$$

where k is observed second order rate constant. The energy and entropy of activation have been calculated to be 18.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and 10.9 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Several kinetic studies on the mechanism of oxidation of α -amino acids both in acid and alkaline media and also in the presence of both metal and non-metal ion catalysts have been reported¹. There are studies where a group of workers indicate formation of aldehyde through the hydrolysis of an imine intermediate whereas the other group reports further oxidation of the imine to nitrile. Third group reports neither aldehydes nor nitriles instead reports formation of α -keto acids. In view of these observations the controversy regarding the identification of the oxidation products of α -amino acids still persists. Alanine is a neutral amino acid in which hydrogen of one of the methyl group is replaced by amino group. These were certain observations that prompted us to undertake the title study mainly from the following view-points

Cerium(IV) – a potential oxidant in perchloric acid has its coordination sites available for incorporation of the amino acid molecule. Whether such coordination is possible via nitrogen of amino group or carboxyl group oxygen will be a useful evidence to analyse the reaction events properly and precisely. Identification and characterization of products are also important for proper elucidation of the reaction mechanism. Kinetic parameters are valuable guide for the same.

Results and discussion

Variation of cerium(IV) The concentration of cerium(IV) was varied from $(7.5 \times 10^{-4}$ to $4.24 \times 10^{-3})$ mol dm⁻³ at different concentrations of alanine viz 3.0×10^{-2} ,

5×10^{-2} and 7.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ respectively at $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ and $[Ag^I] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³. The first order rate constants decrease with increasing concentration of cerium(IV).

Variation of alanine The concentration of alanine was varied from 2.0×10^{-2} to 10×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of $[Ag^I] = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ and $[Ce^{IV}] = 9.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³ at three temperatures viz 50°, 55° and 60°C respectively. The rate of the reaction initially increases and then tends towards a limiting value with further increasing concentration of alanine (Table 1).

Table 1 Observed rate constant for the reaction of alanine and cerium(IV) in HClO₄ medium

$[Ce^{IV}] = 9.7 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³ $[Ag^I] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ $[H^+] = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³

$10^2 [Ala]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 [k] s^{-1}$		
	50°C	55°C	60°C
2.0	4.31	6.71	9.59
3.0	5.75	8.36	12.0
4.0	7.67	9.97	14.2
5.0	9.21	10.9	15.3
6.0	9.83	12.1	16.1
7.0	10.5	12.8	17.0
8.0	11.2	13.4	17.9
9.0	11.5	13.6	17.9
10.0	11.5	13.8	18.2

Variation of silver(I) Silver(I) concentration was varied from 5.0×10^{-4} to 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at constant concentration of $[Ce^{IV}] = 9.4 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, $[Ala] = 5 \times 10^{-2}$

The [adduct]⁺ undergoes an intramolecular electron transfer yielding end products of the oxidation of alanine. The proposed mechanism leads to the rate law (8) accounting for an experimental observations.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k_1 K_1 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{LH}^+][\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}] \quad (8)$$

Since the concentration of Ce^{IV} is governed by equilibrium (3), this free equilibrium concentration of Ce^{IV} in terms of gross analytical concentration will be given eq. (9).

$$\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}} = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h} \quad (9)$$

Similarly [LH⁺] is the free equilibrium concentration amino acid and thus the concentration of Ag^I which is also equilibrium concentration is governed by the eq. (10).

$$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}} = \frac{[\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}] [\text{LH}^+]}{1 + K_1 [\text{LH}^+]} \quad (10)$$

Substituting Ce^{IV} and Ag^I from eqs. (9) and (10) respectively in eq. (8), eq. (11) is obtained

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{LH}^+] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_h) (1 + K_1 [\text{LH}^+])} \quad (11)$$

At constant hydrogen ion concentration and maintaining in pseudo first order conditions the rate eq. (11) reduced to the eq. (12).

$$k^{\text{I}} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{LH}^+] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Ag}^{\text{I}}]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_h) (1 + K_1 [\text{LH}^+])} \quad (12)$$

where k^I is first order rate constant (Table 2). Since the order with respect to silver(I) is one, this equation (eq. (12)) is further reduced to eq. (13).

$$k = \frac{k_1 K_1 [\text{LH}^+] [\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+] + K_h) (1 + K_1 [\text{LH}^+])} \quad (13)$$

where k is second order rate constant.

A plot of 1/k versus [LH⁺]⁻¹ was made from the eq. (13) at constant hydrogen ion concentration that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1). The ratio of intercept and slope of the line yielded the value of K₁ to be 18.3, 22.4 and 30.0 at 50°, 55° and 60°C respectively. The value of K₁ obtained in the title reaction in comparison to K₁ = 20 for the Ce^{IV} glycerol complex⁹ at 50°C. K₁ = 18 and

29 for Ce^{IV}-*cis*-1,2-cyclohexanediol and Ce^{IV}-*trans*-1,2-cyclohexanediol complexes¹⁰ respectively indicates strong complexation in HClO₄ medium.

The activation energy of the reaction was calculated by plotting a graph between log k₁ vs [T]⁻¹ to be (19 ± 1) kJ mol⁻¹ and the entropy of the reaction is determine by plotting a graph between log K₁ vs [T]⁻¹ to be (11 ± 1) kJ mol⁻¹. These values are calculated by thermodynamic equation.

A plot 1/k versus 1/[H⁺] was made from eq. (13) at four different concentrations of alanine that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2). A plot of intercept against 1/[LH⁺], we get again straight line with non zero intercept (Fig. 3). The ratio of intercept and slope of the line yielded the value of K₁ to be 18.0 in agreement with the value of K₁ obtained in case of amino acid variation.

There is a distinct possibility of electron transfer from alanine to cerium(IV) in the presence of silver(I) which can be envisaged from the Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Fig. 1. A plot of k⁻¹ vs [LH⁺]⁻¹ : [Ag^I] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Ce^{IV}] = 9.7 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, temp. = (O) 50°C; (Δ) 55°C; (●) 60°C.

Fig. 2. A plot of k^{-1} vs $[H^+]^{-1}$: $[Ag^I] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Ce^{IV}] = 9.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 50°C ; $[Ala] = (O) 3.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $(\Delta) 4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $(\bullet) 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $(\triangle) 6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig. 3. A plot of intercept vs $[LH^+]^{-1}$.

The complexation of silver(I) through nitrogen of the amino group of alanine was ruled out on the premise that the interaction of an electron deficient metal ion with the nitrogen of the protonated amine group is not a reasonable proposition.

Experimental

The kinetic studies of the oxidation of amino acids by cerium(IV) in perchloric acid medium in the presence of silver(I) as catalyst has been studied by monitoring cerium(IV).

The solution of ceric perchlorate was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate (B.D.H., AnalaR) in perchloric acid (E. Merck) and the solution was standardized by titrating an aliquot of the test solution against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate (E. Merck) solution employing ferroin as an indicator¹¹. The titration was always made in the presence of H_2SO_4 ($\sim 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) to obtain a clear and stable colour change at the equivalence point.

All other reagents were of AnalaR reagent grade and were used as supplied. Doubly-distilled water was employed throughout the study.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out in stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks suspended in a temperature controlled water bath at $50 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ unless stated otherwise. All the components of a reaction mixture except ceric perchlorate were taken in these flasks and the reactions were initiated by adding the desired volume of ceric perchlorate solution. The kinetics of the reaction were monitored by estimating the remaining cerium(IV) in an aliquot sample (5 cm^3) withdrawn from the reaction mixture at regular intervals of time. The aliquot was added into ice-cold dil. H_2SO_4 ($\sim 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and the cerium(IV) was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution employing ferroin as an indicator. The kinetics of the reaction were studied under first order conditions and the triplicate rate measurements were within to $\pm 6\%$.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined with an excess of alanine over cerium(IV) in a thermostated water bath for 24 h. The products were extracted from the reaction mixture with ether. An addition of 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine in the reaction mixture yield brown precipitate of hydrazone derivative of aldehyde on being left at 10°C for 24 h. Nevertheless, aldehyde has earlier been reported to be the oxidation product of alanine by ceric sulphate in the presence of silver(I) as catalyst. Thus the product in perchloric acid medium in the reference reaction is also expected to be an aldehyde, the stoichiometry of the reaction can therefore be represented by eq. (14).

Qualitative tests for aldehyde and CO_2 were positive.

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